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BRAZILIAN JOURNAL OF SCIENTIFIC PRODUCTION

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ABSTRACT

The aim of this paper is to present the Revista Brasileira de Produção Científica (Brazilian Journal of Scientific Production), an interdisciplinary electronic publication, from a historical perspective. Its aims and expectations will be described. In view of the need to disseminate scientific production from the various areas of knowledge, it was created with the aim of publicizing the scientific productions of teachers, students and professionals. The work is methodologically qualitative, with documentary and bibliographic methods.